

Awareness and Perception of Librarians towards Implementation of Internet of Things (Iots) for Library Service Delivery in Federal University Libraries, Northern Nigeria

Maryam Bomoi Zarma¹

Mamza Wavi Pur²

Emmanuel .M.K. Dawha³

Correspondents Address Ramat Library,
University of Maiduguri, Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria
maryambomoi16@gmail.com
ORCID: 0009-0005-8970-2774

Abstract

This study examined the awareness and perception of librarians regarding the implementation of the Internet of Things (IoTs) for library service delivery in Federal University Libraries in Northern Nigeria. Specifically, it assessed librarians' level of awareness, their perception of IoTs applications, and the challenges associated with implementing IoTs technologies. Data were collected using a self-designed questionnaire, validated by three different experts- two from the Department of Library and Information Science and one from test and measurement in the Department of Education Modibbo Adama University, respectively. The reliability coefficient of 0.83 was obtained through Crombach alpha reliability testing from a split-half administered questionnaire to 30 respondents (from FUHSA, FUD, FUKashere, FUWukari and FUGA) outside the research setting. The study adopted a descriptive survey design, targeting 72 librarians across nine federal university libraries, with 64 valid responses analyzed using mean, standard deviation, and Chi-square tests via SPSS v27. Findings revealed that librarians demonstrated a generally high level of awareness and a very positive perception of IoTs, recognizing its potential to enhance service quality, accessibility, automation, and security. However, significant challenges including high implementation costs, limited technical expertise, inadequate training, infrastructure gaps, integration issues, and weak institutional policies hindered adoption. Statistical analysis indicated significant differences in awareness levels across libraries but no significant difference in perception levels. The study concludes that while librarians are optimistic about IoTs integration, successful implementation requires strategic investments in infrastructure, professional training, and clear institutional policies.

Keywords: IoTs, library service delivery, librarians' awareness, perception, Federal University Libraries, Nigeria

Introduction

The rapid advancement of technology has transformed the landscape of library service delivery, creating opportunities for more efficient, user-centered, and automated operations. Among emerging technologies, the Internet of Things (IoTs) has garnered global attention for its potential to revolutionize library management. IoTs refers to a network of interconnected devices that communicate and exchange data in real-time, enabling smart monitoring, automation, and enhanced decision-making (Bansal, 2018). In library contexts, IoTs can facilitate tasks such as real-time tracking of resources, automated borrowing and returning, smart shelving, and improved user experience.

University librarians, as key facilitators of information access, play a critical role in adopting and implementing IoTs-based solutions. Their awareness and perception of these technologies significantly influence the success of integration into library systems. While studies in developed countries have demonstrated the benefits of IoTs in libraries, its adoption in Nigerian academic libraries, particularly in the northern region, remains limited. Factors such as infrastructural gaps, high implementation costs, limited technical skills, and inadequate policy frameworks have slowed the adoption process (Akinwale, 2021; Al-Aklabi, 2019).

Conversely librarians' awareness, perception, and the challenges they face in implementing IoTs is crucial for developing strategies that enhance library services. This study therefore investigates how librarians in Federal University Libraries in Northern Nigeria perceive and understand IoTs, the extent of its application in service delivery, and the barriers hindering its effective adoption. Insights from this research can inform policy, training, and infrastructural development, ultimately promoting a more responsive, innovative, and technology-driven library environment.

Objectives of the Study

1. Level of awareness of librarians on Internet of Things for library service delivery in Federal University Libraries, in Northern Nigeria
2. Perception of librarians on Internet of Things for library service delivery in Federal University Libraries, in Northern Nigeria.
3. Challenges associated with the implementation of the Internet of Things for library service delivery in Federal University Libraries, in Northern Nigeria.

Research Hypotheses

H₀₁. There is no significant difference in the level of awareness of librarians about the implementation of IoTs for library service delivery among Federal University Libraries in Northern Nigeria

H₀₂ There is no significant difference in the perception of librarians on IoTs implementation for library service delivery among Federal University Libraries in Northern Nigeria

H₀₃: The challenges associated with the implementation of IoTs for library service delivery are not statistically significant among Federal University Libraries in Northern Nigeria.

Reviewed of Related Literature

Eiriemiokhale and James (2023) investigated the use of IoTs for quality service delivery in Nigerian university libraries. The study used a descriptive survey design, targeting 37 librarians across three universities, selected through purposive sampling to include those directly involved in library operations. Data were collected using a self-designed questionnaire and analyzed with descriptive statistics (frequency, percentages). Findings indicated that IoTs improved technical service delivery, theft management, and real-time alerts, enhancing operational efficiency. Asim et al. (2024) conducted a study on IoT adoption in medical libraries in Pakistan. Using a mixed-methods design, they surveyed 63 librarians and conducted 10 interviews, with participants selected via purposive sampling. Analysis involved descriptive statistics and thematic analysis. Findings revealed that IoT devices improve operational efficiency, but privacy and maintenance concerns were significant barriers.

The perception of librarians regarding the Internet of Things (IoT) for library service delivery in federal university libraries in Nigeria reflects a combination of growing interest and measured caution. As IoT technologies gain prominence globally for their capacity to transform service delivery through automation, connectivity, and data-driven decision-making, Nigerian librarians particularly those in federal universities demonstrate varied perceptions shaped by differences in technological exposure, institutional infrastructure, and access to training opportunities. These perceptions are not uniform but instead reflect the broader realities of operating within resource-constrained academic environments.

Complementing these findings, Liang and Chen (2020), through a comprehensive review of existing literature, affirmed that IoT technologies hold significant potential for improving library services, particularly in enhancing operational efficiency and service responsiveness. Extending the scope of perception studies beyond librarians, Sinha (2022) investigated the awareness and perceptions of Ph.D. students regarding the execution of IoTs in library services. The study revealed that students were generally aware of IoT applications across various service areas, including user authentication, access control, remote monitoring of library resources, and self-issue and return systems designed to reduce theft. Similarly, Kumar (2023), in a study of students at Kurukshetra University, found that an overwhelming majority of respondents (92.4%) believed that IoTs could improve energy and water management in libraries and significantly reduce the time required for book circulation processes. These user centered perceptions reinforce librarians' awareness of IoTs as a technology capable of aligning library services with evolving user expectations.

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. Adewuyi (2012) is of the view that survey research is comprehensive and systematic in collecting data about the opinions, feelings, attitudes, beliefs, and vital facts on people's motivation and behavior. The target population for the study were seventy-two (72) librarians working in the E-library section of the 9 Federal University Libraries in Northern Nigeria. This is in line with Gall and Borg (2007) affirm that the whole population may be studied when the entire size of the population is small or manageable.

Data were collected using a self-designed questionnaire, validated by three different experts- two from the Department of Library and Information Science and one from test and measurement in the Department of Education Modibbo Adama University, respectively. The reliability coefficient of 0.83 was obtained through Crombach alpha reliability testing from a split-half administered questionnaire to 30 respondents (from FUHSA, FUD, FUKashere, FUWukari and FUGA) outside the research setting. Descriptive statistics which include mean, and standard deviation was used in analyzing the data to answer the three (3) research questions; results were presented in tables. Chi-square was used to test the three (3) null hypotheses, at; 0.05 level of significance using the Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 27.

Presentation of Results

Out of the 72 (100%) questionnaires distributed to the respondents in the libraries included in the study, 64 (88.9%) were completed, returned, and considered valid for analysis, whereas 8 (11.1%) were not returned.

Table 1: A standard deviation on the level of awareness towards the Implementation of (IoT) for Library Services

Table with 4 columns: Statement, Mean, SD, Decision. Rows include statements about IoT awareness and implementation, with corresponding mean scores and decision levels (LL, HL).

SD= Standard Deviation; VHL= Very high level; HL = High level; LL =Low Level; VLL =Very low level

Table 1. shows that the cluster mean obtained was 2.51 ±.76 winch signifies the level of awareness towards the implementation of IoT. For Library Services was high. Specifically, eight out of the ten statements had a mean score of 2.5 and above, indicating general awareness and knowledge of IoT was high. Respondents showed strong familiarity with how IoT devices connect and communicate in real-time (Mean = 2.73),

the use of specific IoTs tools such as RFID and smart shelves (Mean = 2.73), and publications discussing IoTs in library science (Mean = 2.78). Awareness was also evident in the application of IoTs in library environments (Mean = 2.51), asset tracking (Mean = 2.53), automation of book borrowing and return processes (Mean = 2.69), and IoTs's contribution to user data analytics (Mean = 2.58). The finding revealed that awareness of IoTs applications in library services is generally high, there is a gap in foundational knowledge and institutional-level implementation that highlights the need for more foundational education and organizational investment in IoTs technologies.

Table 2: A mean and standard deviation of the Perception towards the Implementation of Internet of Things (IoT) for Library Services

Table with 4 columns: Statement, Mean, SD, Decision. It lists 10 statements about IoT implementation in libraries and their corresponding mean scores and standard deviations, all with a 'VH' (Very High) decision.

SD= Standard Deviation; VHL= Very high level; HL = High level; LL =Low Level; VLL =Very low level

The analysis in Table 2. shows that respondents have a very high level of agreement on the potential benefits of IoTs in academic library services, with a cluster mean of 3.86 ± 1.20. All ten statements recorded mean scores well above 2.5, indicating a broad consensus on the value of IoTs in transforming library operations.

agree that IoTs can be used to automate inventory management (Mean = 3.95), save time, and reduce staff workload (Mean = 3.87), as well as streamline inventory and resource management (Mean = 3.86). There is also clear recognition that IoTs can help in real-time tracking of library materials (Mean = 3.82) and enhance security of library resources and data (Mean = 3.85). Furthermore, the belief that librarians should embrace IoTs as part of innovation (Mean = 3.88) and that IoTs can work well with other digital technologies (Mean = 3.67) further supports the respondents' openness to integrating this technology into library systems. The major findings of the analysis reveal that respondents strongly agree on the potential benefits of IoTs in academic library services, with all statements scoring well above 2.5, indicating widespread support.

Table 3: A mean and standard deviation of the Challenges to Implementing internet of things (IoT) in the Library

Table with 4 columns: Statement, Mean, SD, Decision. Rows include categories like Cost and Infrastructure, Technical Capacity, Integration and Compatibility, and Institutional and Policy Factors.

SD; Standard deviation; SA= strongly agree; A= agree; U= undecided; D= disagree; SD= strongly disagree

Table 3 shows that the calculated cluster mean was 3.73 ± 1.13, which indicates that the challenges to IoTs Implementation in Libraries were 'strongly agreed' by the respondents. Typically, it was revealed that the cost of installing IoTs infrastructure is considered a

moderate to major challenge in libraries (Mean = 3.71). The lack of financial resources to maintain IoTs technologies poses a significant challenge (Mean = 3.71). Implementing IoTs requires substantial changes to physical infrastructure, which is seen as a major challenge (Mean = 3.73). A lack of staff with the technical expertise to manage IoTs technologies is viewed as a major challenge (Mean = 3.00). Inadequate training opportunities for emerging technologies like IoTs are perceived as a very major challenge (Mean = 3.03). The absence of a dedicated IT department capable of handling IoTs is a major challenge (Mean = 3.01).

Difficulty integrating IoTs with existing library systems is identified as a moderate challenge (Mean=3.36). Incompatibility between current library software and IoTs devices is recognized as a minor to moderate challenge (Mean = 2.62). Lack of standardization in IoTs implementation within libraries is a major challenge (Mean = 3.92). Concerns about data privacy related to IoTs use in libraries are a major challenge (Mean = 3.95). The permanent nature of IoTs possibly conflicting with data protection laws is a moderate challenge (Mean = 3.29). Risks of unauthorized data breaches from IoTs devices in libraries are a very major challenge (Mean = 3.03). The absence of a clear institutional policy on digital innovation is a moderate to major challenge (Mean = 3.57). A lack of a regional framework supporting IoTs in libraries is perceived as a very major challenge (Mean = 3.03). Resistance from staff due to fear of technological change is viewed as a major challenge (Mean = 3.01). The findings reveal that libraries face significant challenges in implementing IoTs technologies, particularly in areas of cost, technical capacity, system integration, privacy, and institutional policy. With all items scoring above the threshold, these challenges are perceived as strongly agree to very major by respondents.

Table 4a: Contingency table on significant difference in the level of awareness of librarians about the implementation of IoTs for library service delivery among Federal University Libraries in Northern Nigeria

Table with 9 columns: Variables, VH, H, L, VL, and two columns for FO and FE under each. Rows include awareness levels like 'I know the concept of the Internet of Things (IoT)' and 'Staff attending IoTs training/seminars'.

IoTs can automate book borrowing and returning	10	10.4	38	30.5	11	14.8	5	8.3
IoTs contributes to user data analytics	15	10.4	30	30.5	10	14.8	9	8.3
Aware of publications on IoTs in library science	12	10.4	42	30.5	7	14.8	3	8.3
Institution has introduced IoTs-based library services	8	10.4	10	30.5	30	14.8	16	8.3
Total	104	104.0	305	305.0	148	148.0	83	83.0

Table 4b. Summary of Chi-Square test on significant difference in the level of awareness of librarians about the implementation of IoTs for library service delivery among Federal University Libraries in Northern Nigeria.

Variables	VH	H	L	VL	TOTAL	X2	Df	p-value	Decision P<0.05
Observed	9	28	18	9	64(100)	31.77	10	0.002	Significant
Expected	10.4	30.5	14.8	8.3	64(100)	31.77	10	0.002	

The Chi-Square test was conducted to determine whether there is a significant difference in the level of awareness of librarians regarding the implementation of Internet of Things (IoTs) for library service delivery among Federal University Libraries in Northern Nigeria. The result shows a Chi-Square (χ^2) value of 31.77 with 10 degrees of freedom and a p-value of 0.002. Since the p-value (0.002) is less than the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected. This indicates that there is a statistically significant difference in the level of awareness of librarians about the implementation of IoTs for library service delivery among Federal University Libraries in Northern Nigeria. The observed frequencies across the awareness categories (Very High, High, Low, and Very Low) differ noticeably from the expected frequencies, suggesting that librarians do not share a uniform level of awareness. A larger proportion of respondents fall within the High awareness category, while fewer librarians exhibit Very High or Very Low awareness levels. This variation accounts for the significant Chi-Square value obtained

Table 5a Contingency table on significant difference in the perception of librarians on IoTs implementation for library service delivery among Federal University Libraries in Northern Nigeria.

Table with 9 columns: Variables, VH (FO, FE), H (FO, FE), L (FO, FE), VL (FO, FE). Rows include various IoT implementation statements and a Total row.

Table 5b Summary of Chi-Square test on significant difference in the perception of librarians on IoTs implementation for library service delivery among Federal University Libraries in Northern Nigeria.

Table with 10 columns: Variables, VH, H, L, VL, TOTAL, X2, DF, p-value, Decision P<0.05. Rows include Observed and Expected data.

A Chi-square test was carried out to examine whether there is a significant difference in the perception levels of librarians regarding the implementation of the Internet of Things (IoT) for library service delivery among Federal University Libraries in Northern Nigeria.

H03: There is no significant difference in the mean rating of challenges associated with IoT implementation for library service delivery among Federal University Libraries in Northern Nigeria.

Table 6: One-sample t-test table on significant difference in the mean rating of challenges associated with IoT implementation for library service delivery among Federal University Libraries in Northern Nigeria.

Table with 6 columns: Challenges, Mean, Std., t-value, df, p-value. Lists various challenges like 'The cost of installing IoT infrastructure is too high' and their corresponding statistical values.

I am concerned about the data privacy implications of using IoTs in libraries	3.95	1.16	6.83	66	<0.001
IoT's permanent nature may conflict with data protection regulations	3.29	1.50	1.73	66	<0.088
IoT's devices in libraries may lead to unauthorized data breaches	3.03	1.02	8.53	66	<0.001
Our institution lacks a clear policy for digital innovation	3.57	1.36	3.63	66	<0.001
There is no regional framework supporting IoTs in libraries	3.03	0.93	9.13	66	<0.001
Staff may resist the adoption of IoTs due to fear of technological change	3.01	0.93	8.83	66	<0.001

The results of the one-sample t-test indicate that the mean ratings of challenges associated with IoTs implementation are significantly different from 3 (the neutral point), with a p-value of < 0.001. This suggests that librarians perceive the challenges associated with IoTs implementation as significant barriers to adoption. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of challenges associated with IoTs implementation.

Discussion of Findings

The finding that librarians strongly agree on the potential benefits of IoTs in academic library services, including enhancing service quality, accessibility, automation, and security, aligns with the study by Eiriemokhale (2023), which explored librarians' perceptions of IoTs in Nigerian academic libraries. The study found that librarians acknowledged the potential of IoTs in enhancing library functions such as inventory management, resource tracking, and environmental control. Similarly, the current study's findings suggest that librarians recognize the benefits of IoTs in improving library services, including personalized services, smart space management, and enhanced security. The optimism expressed by librarians about implementing IoTs in academic library services despite infrastructural challenges in Nigeria is notable.

The perceived benefits of IoTs in academic library services, including enhanced service quality, accessibility, automation, and security, are consistent with the literature on the applications of IoTs in libraries. IoTs systems can also enable customized book recommendations and notifications for new arrivals, events, or workshops (Adirati, 2023). Overall, the study's findings highlight the need for library administrators to invest in IoTs infrastructure and provide training and support for librarians to effectively implement IoTs technology in academic libraries. By doing so, libraries can harness the potential benefits of IoTs to improve service delivery, enhance user experience, and optimize library operations.

The calculated cluster mean was 3.73 ± 1.13 , which indicates that the challenges to IoTs Implementation in Libraries were strongly agreed by Federal University Libraries, in Northern Nigeria. This is in line with the work of Al-Aklabi (2019) also noted that the use of IoTs technology may cause concerns about data privacy and security, which can be

addressed through the development of clear policies and guidelines. Overall, the study's findings highlight the need for libraries to invest in infrastructure, provide training and support for librarians, and develop clear policies and guidelines to address the challenges associated with IoTs implementation. By addressing these challenges, libraries can harness the potential benefits of IoTs technology to improve service delivery, enhance user experience, and optimize library operations. The study's findings also show that librarians are aware of the potential benefits of IoTs technology, but they also recognize the significant challenges associated with its implementation.

Findings reveal that show that there is a statistically significant difference in the perception levels of librarians toward IoTs implementation in library service delivery within the sampled institutions this has corroborated to the work of Fasola, Oyadeyi, and Iyoro (2023) examined awareness, acceptance, and readiness to use Internet of things technology among academic librarians in Nigerian university libraries and found that librarians not only demonstrated awareness of IoTs but also showed varying degrees of acceptance and readiness to adopt it for library service delivery, with significant relationships between awareness, acceptance, and preparedness to use the technology ($p < 0.05$). This suggests that librarians' attitudes toward IoTs implementation are influenced by individual and contextual factors, reflecting heterogeneous perception levels.

The findings shows that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of challenges associated with IoTs implementation. This has related to the work of Oke, Arowoia, and Akomolafe (2020), who conducted a quantitative survey with professionals in the Nigerian construction industry using a structured questionnaire on a five-point Likert scale to assess challenges to IoTs adoption.

Conclusion

The study examined the awareness and perception of librarians towards the implementation of the Internet of Things (IoT) for library service delivery in Federal University Libraries in Northern Nigeria, the librarians show a high level of awareness and a very positive perception of Internet of Things (IoT) technologies for library service delivery. They recognize IoT's potential to enhance service quality, streamline operations, improve accessibility, and strengthen security. However, implementation remains limited by challenges such as high costs, inadequate technical skills, insufficient training, infrastructure gaps, system integration issues, and weak institutional policies. To fully harness IoT's benefits, libraries must invest in modern infrastructure, provide targeted training, and develop clear policies that support the adoption and sustainable use of IoT technologies in library services.

Recommendations

1. Libraries should prioritize the acquisition and installation of IoTs technologies, including smart shelves, sensors, environmental monitoring systems, and automated service platforms. Such investments will enable real-time resource tracking, improve accessibility, and support personalized services for library users.
2. Librarians' optimism about IoTs is counterbalanced by concerns over technological complexity. Continuous professional development programs should be organized to train library staff on the operation, maintenance, and potential applications of IoTs systems.
3. Libraries management should conduct pilot implementations of IoTs systems to evaluate feasibility, cost-effectiveness, and staff readiness. Pilot projects can identify challenges early, provide evidence for decision-making, and allow gradual scaling while minimizing risks.
4. Universities and library management should explore public-private partnerships, donor support, and collaborations with technology providers to offset costs. Adequate IT support, network infrastructure, and technical assistance should be put in place to sustain the IoTs systems.
5. To maximize impact, IoTs should not be implemented in isolation but integrated with existing library management systems, digital repositories, and user services. This integration ensures seamless workflows, enhances operational efficiency, and provides an improved user experience.
6. Libraries should establish mechanisms to regularly monitor IoTs performance, collect feedback from users and staff, and assess the impact on service delivery. Evaluation metrics could include service speed, resource availability, user satisfaction, and operational efficiency.

Reference

- Abdulkareem, M. Y., Oduwole, T. R., & Abubakar, A. O. (2025). Librarians' readiness and perception towards the implementation of smart library systems in Kwara State, Nigeria. *Nasarawa Journal of Library and Information Science*, 9(1), 109–119. Retrieved from <https://najlisnuk.ng/index.php/najis/article/view/277>
- Akintunde, M. O., & Amuda, H. O. (2024). Predictors of adoption of blockchain technology by academic libraries in Nigeria. *Library Hi Tech*, 43(4–5), 1273–1291. doi:10.1108/LHT-06-2023-0247
- Arebamen Eiriemiokhale, K., & James, J. B. (2023). Application of the Internet of Things for quality service delivery in Nigerian university libraries. *Indian Journal of Information Sources and Services*, 13(1), 17–25. <https://doi.org/10.51983/ijiss-2023.13.1.3463>
- Asim, M., Arif, M., Rafiq, M., Nawaz, M. A., & Ahmad, R. (2024). Investigating applications of Internet of Things in medical libraries of Pakistan: An empirical study. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 50(5), 102925. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acalib.2024.102925>
- Bansal, A., Arora, D., & Suri, A. (2018). *Internet of Things: Beginning of new era for libraries. Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. Available at DigitalCommons@University of Nebraska–Lincoln.

- Eiriemiokhale, A., & James, K. (2023). Application of IoTs technologies for quality service delivery in Nigerian university libraries. *International Journal of Library & Information Services*, 13(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.4018/IJLIS.2023010101>
- Fasola, O. S., Oyadeyi, A. E., & Iyoro, A. O. (2024). *Awareness, acceptance and readiness to use Internet of Things technology for library services in academic libraries in Nigeria. Communicate: Journal of Library and Information Science*, 26(1), 270–288.
- Gall, M. D., & Borg, W. R. (2007). *Educational research: An introduction* (8th ed.). Pearson.
- Ghazaleh, S. (2019). *Institutional policy and standardization issues influencing IoTs deployment in libraries* (Unpublished doctoral dissertation). University of Ibadan, Nigeria.
- Kumar, R. B. T. S. (2023). Students' perceptions of IoT application for library service automation: A case study of Kurukshetra University. *Open Information Science*. <https://doi.org/10.1515/opis-2022-0154>
- Liang, X., & Chen, Y. (2018). Libraries in the Internet of Things (IoT) era. *Library Hi Tech*, 38(1), 79–93. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LHT-11-2017-0233>
- Opele, J. K. (2021). *Application of Internet of Things (IoT) technology in library services. JEWEL Journals*. (Review of IoTs applications in libraries)
- Yusuf, F. O., Ifijeh, G., & Owolabi, S. (2019). Awareness of Internet of Things and its potential in enhancing academic library service delivery in a developing country. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*, 1–11. Retrieved from <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/2831/>